

Teachers' Communication Skills as Predictor of Students Academic Achievement in Financial Accounting in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

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ABSTRACT: This study examined teachers' communication skills as predictor of students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research question guided the study and two null hypothesis formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 569 senior secondary school SS2. Accounting students in 267 public secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Anambra State. The entire 569 SS II students were used as the population was manageable as a result, census sampling technique was adopted. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: Teachers' Communication Skills Questionnaire (TCSQ). The scores of the students were used to measure students' academic achievement. The instrument was subjected to face and construct validity. The reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha correlation coefficient. The coefficient value of 0.81 was obtained. The data collected were analyzed using simple linear regression. The findings of study revealed the verbal and non-verbal teachers' communication skills play a critical role in students' academic achievement in financial Accounting. Strong verbal skills enhance clarity, engagement and comprehension, while non-verbal communication supports effective classroom interactions. The study recommended among others that accounting teachers in the SS II schools should strategize their efforts towards using effective verbal and none-verbal engagement for better academic achievement. The study contributed to the body of knowledge by highlighting the necessity for effective teacher-student communication such as verbal, non-verbal and listening communication skills for better students' academic performance in Financial Accounting.

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Communication, Communication Skills, Academic Achievement, Skills

INTRODUCTION

In educational settings, teachers impact knowledge into their students for the achievement of educational objectives. The achievement of these educational objectives are made manifest in student through their academic achievements. The ineffectiveness of teacher in classroom interaction with the students could affect the students' academic achievement. Academic achievement refers to what a student has achieved in different subjects of study. Okoro (2021) defined academic achievement as the sum total of information gained after completing a course of instruction (partially or fully) which is measurable with the use of achievement test. Academic achievement is the overall academic performance of students in the school. Academic achievement has been seen as the educational goal that is achieved by students, teachers or institutions over a period of time. It is the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has attained their short or long-term educational goals and is measured either by continuous assessment or cumulative grade point average (CGPA) (Nwalo & Eze, 2022).

Generally, academic achievement may be assessed by the use of achievement tests. Achievement is reflected by the extent to which skill or knowledge has been acquired by a person through the training imparted to him/her. If the educational system should prepare young people adequately for challenges and demands of 21st century, then better academic achievement should be downplayed. Maitala, et. al.,

(2023) opined that academic achievement is measured using different means and methods and approaches which ultimately result in high, low or average performance. In secondary schools, a student's academic achievement determines his progress in his studies and justifies or quantifies him to move to the next level. Green and Owo (2022) opined that academic achievement helps to screen students' current level of academic functioning as well as the extent to which they have acquired the knowledge and skills more than their counterparts of the same age or class.

In Nigeria, poor academic achievement at the secondary school level of education is on the increase. In Anambra State, Onyeka and Okoye (2023) noted that in 2020, 62.9% obtained credits and above in Financial Accounting and 37.1% recorded poor performance. In 2021, 81.2% obtained credits and above in Financial Accounting while 18.8% recorded poor performance. In 2022, 76.4% obtained credits and above in Financial Accounting and 23.6% recorded poor performance. This rising and falling in the students' achievement may be attributed to the method of teaching used by teachers in teaching Financial Accounting. However, most teachers do not appreciate their roles in the classroom and these invariably affect the quality of teaching and learning in the educational system. Apparently, the teachers have been blamed for not improving students' achievement in Financial accounting due to lack of appropriate communication skills required for good teaching and learning process.

Financial accounting is the process of recording, classifying, selecting, measuring, interpreting, summarizing and reporting financial information of an organization to internal and external users for decision-making and proper appraisal. It is defined by Mbusube (2022) as the art of recording, classifying and summarizing in a significant manner and in terms of money, transactions and events which are, in part at least, of a financial character and interpreting the results thereof. Okafor and Nzukwe (2019) defined financial accounting as the process of recording financial transactions pertaining to a business. The financial accounting process includes summarizing, analyzing and reporting these transactions to oversight agencies, regulators and tax collection entities. Financial Accounting is a skill-based subject that requires the active participation of learners. It is the process of recording, reporting and evaluating economic occurrences and transactions that affect business organizations and the general economic status of a nation. Introductory accounting subject is a stepping-stone for non-accounting students to acquire fundamental knowledge of accounting concepts.

The financial statements used in accounting practices are a concise summary of financial transactions over an accounting period, summarizing a company's operations, financial position and cash flows. Financial Accounting is not a subject that can be mastered by mere memorization, it requires continuous practice. Thus, this situation calls for remedial action by using a teaching technique that encourages active participation of learners to improve academic achievement in Financial Accounting. Poor achievement of students in financial accounting can be attributed to the poor application of teachers' communication skills in classroom teaching appropriate teaching methods. Teachers manner of approach and method of teaching talk volumes towards students' academic engagement. A teacher may be highly intelligent and qualified, but would not have the ability to inculcate knowledge and competencies into others because he/she cannot communicate well using the appropriate teaching methods. A teacher even if he has all the degrees it takes to be a professional but lack adequate communication skill with relevant teaching methods, he or she is of no importance in academic environment.

Teachers' communication skills are most vital for interactions with students because the act of teaching itself requires competence in skills. This is true because, teachers are responsible for comprehending and breaking down complex information, conveying these information clearly to students (both verbally and in written resources), presenting them in a manner that sustains their attention to resolving their questions or problems (Sword, 2020). Teachers' communication skills refer to behaviors through which teachers can interact with students and other staff in a way that leads to positive responses and avoid negative ones. Given the importance of communication skills in improving the academic well-being of students, recognizing its affective factors is one of the main necessities in the school system.

Communication skill as speaking appropriately to people while maintaining good eye contact, eloquent speech with tailored language, listening effectively, writing clearly with concise language, being confident, friendliness, empathy, use of question, open mindedness and presenting one's ideas appropriately (Manafa, 2018). Abbass (2017) noted that communication skill is vital because members focus on standard to know what they are expected to do, what standards of performance are expected of them and how long they have to do any job assigned to them. Manafa (2018) in addition, asserted that poor usage of communication skills in secondary schools in Anambra State has been a great concern to the school management and members of staff. Manafa further observed that most school principals refuse to have listening ears to the members of staff and are not competent to use clear and straight forward language while giving out information, thereby bringing confusion, tension and conflicts in the school.

Communication skills of teachers are the basic need of academic achievement of students and professional success of life. Students need to understand what is right and what is wrong which totally depend upon the nature of communication skills teachers adopt in classrooms (Abam & Monity, 2023). Nwite and Eze (2016) outlined communication skills to include verbal skill and non-verbal communicate skills. The verbal communication skill is the ability of teachers to express or exchange thoughts or information through sound, words or

speech in the classroom. Angelika (2018) referred to verbal communication skills as the ability to communicate effectively through speech. This communication skill enables the teachers (financial accounting teachers inclusive) to appropriately drill students to the appropriate rudiments of solving accounting problems.

Financial Accounting teacher application of verbal skills is essential in rendering professional advice, assistance, guidance and counseling services to members of staff. Examples of verbal communication include: face-to-face conversation and use of electronic media for oral conversations among others. Verbal communication is the interaction achieved through speaking and conversation. Good speaking skill requires non-verbal communication such as listening, attitude, gestures, facial expression and others to complete its impact on the audience. Non-verbal communication is often more subtle and more effective than verbal communication and can convey better meaning than words.

On the other hand, non-verbal communication is the act of conveying information without the use of words. This might involve using certain facial expressions or hand gestures to make a specific point, or it could involve the use (or non-use) of eye contact, physical proximity and other nonverbal cues to get a message across. Obilor (2021) defined non-verbal communication skills as the ability to convey meaning without the use of words either written or spoken. In other words, any communication made between two or more persons through the use of facial expressions, hand movements, body language, postures and gestures is called non-verbal communication. Non-verbal communication is important because it gives valuable information about a situation, including how a person might be feeling, how someone receives information and how to approach a person or group of people. An accounting teacher can use non-verbal cues by listening attentively while delivering his subject matter, this will help him easily know when the students are understanding his teaching and when they are not.

Until today, questions about effectiveness of teachers' communication skills and teaching methods on students' learning have consistently raised considerable interest in the thematic field of education research. Furthermore, the problem of poor academic achievement especially in Financial Accounting had assumed a worrisome dimension in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is so because the overall achievement in internal and external examinations over the years continues to fluctuate despite the investments made by government in the public secondary schools. There has been issue of challenges of teachers' poor classroom communication skills as impediments to students understanding of a concept tutored. All attempts both by stakeholders and governments to provide textbooks, instructional materials, pay salary in time towards finding possible solutions to raise students character in learning had not improve this ugly school outcome. It is based on these that this study seeks to ask the question; to what extent do teachers' classroom communication skills predict students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Financial Accounting is one of the subjects that is vital for the students' future career. Despite the significant financial investments made by the Nigerian government particularly in Anambra State to enhance financial accounting in public secondary schools, the expected outcomes in students' academic performance remain disappointingly low. This mismatch between expenditure and academic returns has raised critical concerns about the underlying causes of the persistent decline in students' academic achievement, alongside the increasing display of negative attitudes and diminished moral values among secondary school students. One plausible explanation for this educational inefficiency lies in the quality of instructional delivery, with particular emphasis on the communication skills of teachers. Since communication is foundational to effective teaching, classroom management, and the overall learning process, deficiencies in this area may significantly undermine students' academic success. Reports from public secondary schools in Anambra State indicate that many teachers exhibit poor communication behaviours such as ineffective language use, verbal hostility, inattentiveness to student feedback, inappropriate non-verbal cues, and generally unfriendly demeanour which compromise teacher-student interactions and the learning environment. These observed lapses call into question the communicative competence of accounting teachers as a determinant of students' academic achievement. Therefore, the problem this study seeks to investigate is the extent to which accounting teachers' communication skills predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine teachers' communication skills as predictor of students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. determine verbal communication skills as a predictor of students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. examine non-verbal communication skills as a predictor of students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. What is the predictive value of verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of non-verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study:

Ho₁. Verbal communication skills do not significantly predict financial accounting students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Ho₂. Non-verbal communication skills do not significantly predict financial accounting students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State

METHODS

The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 569 senior secondary school in SS2. Accounting students in 267 public secondary schools in the six Education Zones of Anambra State. The sample consisted 569 as the entire population was used as the sample size of the study. The instrument for data collection was self-structured questionnaire titled: Teachers' Communication Skills Questionnaire (TCSQ). It has three Clusters 'B1-B3.' Cluster 'B1' elicits information on verbal communication skill with 10-items; Cluster 'B2' elicits information on non-verbal communication skill with 10-items; and Cluster 'B3' elicits information on listening communication skill with 10-items. All the Clusters 'B1-B3' in the instrument 'TCSQ' have a total of 30-items. The items were placed on a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The range of scores were weighted as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The scores of the students were used to measure students' academic achievement. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validity. The reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha correlation coefficient. The average coefficient value of the questionnaire was 0.81. This showed a value which indicated a positive and high reliability. Five hundred and sixty-nine (569) copies of the questionnaires were administered and five hundred and fifty eight (558) copies were retrieved which showed 558(98.07%) return rate. The data collected were analyzed using simple linear regression and the statistical package of social science (SPSS 26). The data collected were analyzed using simple and multiple linear regression analysis.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the predictive value of verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of the Regression Results of the Predictive Value of Verbal Communication Skill on Students' Academic Achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta(β)	t	
(Constant)	0.050	0.723		0.069	High Positive Predictive Value
Verbal Communication Skills	0.917	0.231	0.740	3.970	

R= 0.740, R Square = 0.548, Adjusted R²=.513, F = 15.762.

Table 1 shows the summary of the regression results of the predictive value of verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The results revealed that the R= 0.740, R Square = 0.548, Adjusted R²= 0.513, F = 15.762. This result indicated a high positive predictive value of verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State because verbal communication skill has 54.8% predictive value on students' academic achievement. This implies that teachers' verbal communication skill has a high positive predictive value on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of non-verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of the Regression Results of the Predictive Value of Non-Verbal Communication Skill on Students' Academic Achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta(β)	t	
(Constant)	0.943	0.756		1.248	Moderate Positive Predictive Value
Non-verbal Communication Skills	0.733	0.282	0.585	2.603	

R= 0.585, R Square = 0.343, Adjusted R²= 0.292, F = 6.774.

Table 2 shows the summary of the regression results of the predictive value of non-verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The results revealed that the R= 0.585, R Square = 0.343, Adjusted R²= 0.292, F = 6.774. This result indicated a moderate positive predictive value of non-verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State because non-verbal communication skill has 34.3% predictive value on students' academic achievement in Financial; Accounting. This suggests non-verbal communication skill has a moderate positive predictive value on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H₀: Verbal communication skills do not significantly predict financial accounting students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 3: Summary of the Regression Results of the Predictive Value of Verbal Communication Skill on Students' Academic Achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta(β)	t		
(Constant)	0.050	0.723		0.069	0.002	Significant
Verbal Communication Skills	0.917	0.231	0.740	3.970		

R= 0.740, R Square = 0.548, Adjusted R²= .513, F = 15.762.

Table 3 shows the summary of the regression results of the predictive value of verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The results revealed that the R= 0.740, R Square = 0.548, Adjusted R²= 0.513, F = 15.762. This result indicated a high positive predictive value of verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State because verbal communication skill has 54.8% predictive value on students' academic achievement. More so, the p-value (0.002) is below the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was retained. Therefore, verbal communication skills significantly predict financial accounting students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2

H₀: Non-verbal communication skills do not significantly predict financial accounting students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 4: Summary of the Regression Results of the Predictive Value of Non-Verbal Communication Skill on Students' Academic Achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta(β)	t		
(Constant)	0.943	0.756		1.248	.022	Significant
Non-verbal Communication Skills	0.733	0.282	0.585	2.603		

R= 0.585, R Square = 0.343, Adjusted R²= 0.292, F = 6.774.

Table 4 shows the summary of the regression results of the predictive value of non-verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The results revealed that the R= 0.585, R Square = 0.343, Adjusted R²= 0.292, F = 6.774. This result indicated a moderate positive predictive value of non-verbal communication skill on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State because non-verbal communication skill has 34.3% predictive value on students' academic achievement in Financial; Accounting. More so, the p-value (0.022) is below the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was retained. Therefore, non-verbal communication skills significantly predict financial accounting students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of the study as shown in table 1 revealed that teachers' verbal communication skill has a high positive predictive value on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The results of the corresponding null hypothesis in table 8 showed that teachers' verbal communication skill has a significant predictive value on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. These findings suggested that teachers' verbal communication skills play a crucial role in shaping students' academic performance in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that teachers who clearly articulate accounting concepts, provide effective explanations and engage students verbally contribute significantly to their understanding and mastery of the subject. The predictive value indicates that students' success in Financial Accounting can be largely anticipated based on the effectiveness of their teachers' verbal interactions. Consequently, enhancing teachers' communication skills could lead to improved academic outcomes, reinforcing the importance of professional development in pedagogical communication.

In line with these findings, Abam and Monity (2023) found that effective verbal communication facilitates knowledge transfer, enhances comprehension and promotes student engagement. Teachers who articulate accounting concepts clearly enable students to grasp complex topics such as ledger balancing, double-entry bookkeeping and financial statement preparation with ease. Similarly, Esiaba (2023) found that students exposed to teachers with strong verbal communication skills demonstrated higher retention and application of accounting principles in examinations. Additionally, verbal clarity minimizes misconceptions and promotes active classroom interactions, which are essential in understanding Financial Accounting. Furthermore, Yasmin, et. al., (2023) attested that teachers who use effective questioning techniques, elaboration and real-life examples significantly enhance students' analytical skills in accounting. These findings align with the cognitive learning theory, which posits that verbal communication enhances the encoding, storage and retrieval of information. Teachers' verbal communication as Ikpa and Obilor (2022) findings affirmed also fosters an interactive learning environment, which encourages students to seek clarification and express their understanding. In Financial Accounting, where precision is crucial, effective verbal explanations help students correct errors and refine their problem-solving strategies. Ajuwon (2022) finding attested that students taught by articulate teachers exhibit better problem-solving skills and conceptual understanding compared to those taught by less communicative instructors. In addition, effective communication enhances teacher-student rapport, which increases student motivation and classroom participation, leading to better academic outcomes.

More so, the findings of the study as shown in table 2 revealed that teachers' non-verbal communication skill has a moderate positive predictive value on students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The results of the corresponding null hypothesis in table 9 showed that teachers' non-verbal communication skill significantly predicts students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. These findings showed that dedicated that teachers' non-verbal communication skills, such as facial expressions, gestures, eye contact and body language, play a crucial role in influencing students' academic performance in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Non-verbal cues help reinforce verbal explanations, enhance clarity and create an engaging classroom environment that promotes better understanding. Effective use of non-verbal communication also fosters teacher-student rapport, boosts student motivation and maintains classroom

discipline. This implies that teachers who skillfully utilize non-verbal expressions can positively impact students' comprehension, retention and application of accounting concepts, leading to improved academic achievement.

The significance of teachers' non-verbal communication skills in predicting students' academic achievement in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools in Anambra State can be attributed to various factors. In agreement with this finding, Ukaigwe and Jack (2020) findings attested that non-verbal communication, which includes gestures, facial expressions, eye contact and body language, enhances the learning process by reinforcing verbal explanations and ensuring better comprehension of complex accounting concepts. Yakubu and Afolabi (2020) finding affirmed that when teachers use appropriate gestures and facial expressions while explaining accounting principles such as ledger balancing and financial statement preparation, students are more likely to engage actively and retain the information. Non-verbal communication as Ayoro and Onyeike (2020) found out also helps in managing classroom dynamics effectively. Teachers who maintain eye contact and use affirmative body language create an atmosphere of attentiveness and discipline, reducing distractions and improving students' focus. This is particularly crucial in Financial Accounting, where precision and attentiveness to detail are required. In agreement with this finding, Oyewole, et. al., (2020) found that students in classrooms where teachers utilize effective non-verbal cues show higher levels of motivation and interest in the subject, which translates into better academic performance.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, teachers' communication skills as effective teaching methods play a critical role in students' academic achievement in financial Accounting. Strong verbal and listening skills enhance clarity, engagement and comprehension, while non-verbal communication supports effective classroom interactions. Therefore, fostering effective communication and adopting interactive teaching strategies are essential for maximizing students' academic performance in Financial Accounting in public secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and education authorities should organize training programs to improve teachers' verbal, non-verbal and listening communication skills to enhance teachers' ability to engage students effectively in Financial Accounting.
2. Accounting teachers should apply professional charisma to create an interactive classroom environment where students feel comfortable in asking questions and participating in discussions and solving accounting problems to improve their learning outcomes.

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